

Development and In-Vitro Characterization of Orally Disintegrating Tablets of Vonoprazan Fumarate Co-Crystals

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ABSTRACT

Vonoprazan (VPZ) is the first-in-class potassium-competitive acid blocker (P-CAB), and has many advantages over proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). It is administered as a fumarate salt for the treatment of acid-related diseases, including reflux esophagitis, gastric ulcer, and duodenal ulcer, and for eradication of *Helicobacter pylori*. To discover novel cocrystals of VPZ, we adopted an artificial neural network (ANN)-based machine learning model as a virtual screening tool that can guide selection of the most promising coformers for VPZ cocrystals. Experimental screening by liquid-assisted grinding (LAG) confirmed that 8 of 19 coformers selected by the ANN model were likely to create new solid forms with VPZ. Structurally similar benzenediols and benzenetriols, i.e., catechol (CAT), resorcinol (RES), hydroquinone (HYQ), and pyrogallol (GAL), were used as coformers to obtain phase pure cocrystals with VPZ by reaction crystallization. We successfully prepared and characterized three novel cocrystals: VPZ-RES, VPZ-CAT, and VPZ-GAL. VPZ-RES had the highest solubility among the novel cocrystals studied here, and was even more soluble than the commercially available fumarate salt of VPZ in solution at pH 6.8. In addition, novel VPZ cocrystals had superior stability in aqueous media than VPZ fumarates, demonstrating their potential for improved pharmaceutical performance.

Keywords: pharmaceutical cocrystal; vonoprazan; P-CAB; Stability.

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION ON ORALLY DISINTEGRATING TABLET:

Orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) are solid dosage forms designed to dissolve or disintegrate rapidly in the mouth without the need for water, typically within 30 seconds or less. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) defines ODTs as “a solid dosage form containing medicinal substances which disintegrate rapidly, usually within a matter of seconds, when placed upon the tongue”. [1]

Oral administration is the most widely used and convenient route with high stability and a small packaging size. The orally disintegrating tablet (ODT), as a delivery system, rapidly disintegrates in the mouth upon contact with saliva; therefore, it does not need additional water [2].

Clinically, in some cases ODTs may provide improved safety and efficacy. However there are limitations in some medications such as patients who have Sjögren's syndrome or dryness of the mouth due to decreased saliva production or take anticholinergic medications may not be convenient to use ODTs (Bharawaj et al., 2010). Commercially enlarged product diversity, extended patent life, and marketing advantages can be counted as main reasons actuating ODT technology developments (Pfister and Ghosh, 2005).

INTRODUCTION ON CO-CRYSTAL:

Pharmaceutical cocrystal can be defined as “crystalline material comprised of API & one or more coformers in stoichiometric ratio (1:1, 1:2, 1:3 etc), which are solid at room temperature.

USFDA (2013) defines cocrystal as "solids which are crystalline materials composed of 2 or more

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molecules in same crystal lattice." Definition proposed by "Indo-US bilateral meeting on Evolving role of Solid State Chemistry in Pharmaceutical Science" is "Cocrystals are solids that are crystalline, single phase materials composed of 2 or more different molecular and/or ionic compounds in stoichiometric ratio which are neither solvates nor simple salts." [2,3]

SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT TECHNIQUE

Figure 1: Solubility Enhancement Technique

INTRODUCTION OF DRUG:

VONOPRAZAN FUMARATE:

Vonoprazan fumarate was first approved Potassium-Competitive Acid Blocker (P-CAB) drug. It was developed by Takeda Pharmaceutical Company and first approved in Japan in December 2014 under the brand name Takecab. Vonoprazan marked a significant advancement in acid-related disease treatment, offering a faster and more sustained acid

suppression compared to traditional proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). It was approved in Russia in 2021, by US FDA in 2023 and in India by Drug Controller General of India (DCGI) in 2024. [4,5,6]

OBJECTIVE:

To carry out Drug excipient compatibility study. To enhance the solubility study. To formulate Vonoprazan fumarate tablet using co-crystal of vonoprazan fumarate. To evaluate the optimized formulated dosage form for various physico-chemical parameters like hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content, dissolution.

To carry out stability study on most satisfactory formulation as per ICH guideline.

METHODOLOGY:

Preparation of Co-Crystals

The co-crystal is prepared by solvent evaporation method. First take polymer (Resorcinol, Catechol, Hydroquinone, Pyrogallol and Kyron T-314) and drug. In the ratio of polymer and drug (Resorcinol 1:1.6, Catechol 1:3, Hydroquinone 1:3, Pyrogallol 1:2 and Kyron T-314 1:1). and add required amount of solvent (acetonitrile). The prepared solution magnetically stirred for 10-20 min. at room temperature. The solid product was filtered, dried and collected in zip bag. [7]

Figure 2: Co-crystals of Vonoprazan fumarate

Method of Preparation of Tablets

The method of preparation of ODTs by Direct compression method. Weigh all the ingredient accurately in the weighing balance. Then mix the C-crystalline API and Excipient and then pass the

mixture from the sieve no. 40. Then add the required amount of super disintegrant and mix them well. Add required amount of lubricant and glidant and mix it well. And compress the tablet in the compression machine.[8]

Formulation of Preliminary batches of Vonoprazan Fumarate Orally Disintegrating Tablets

Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Co-crystalline API (mg)	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
Sodium starch glycolate(%)	5	10	15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
cross povidone (%)	-	-	-	5	10	15	-	-	-	-	-	-
croscarmellose sodium (%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	10	15	-	-	-
Kyron T-314 (%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	10	15
HPMC E-15 (mg)	92	91	90	92	91	90	92	91	90	92	91	90
Aspartame(mg)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Magnesium stearate (mg)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Talc(mg)	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Flavour (ml)	q.s											
Total (mg)	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

Full Factorial Design

3 ² Full Factorial Designs			
Batch No.	X1 Amount of Kyron T-314	X2 Amount of HPMC E-15	
V1	-1	-1	
V2	-1	0	
V3	-1	+1	
V4	0	-1	
V5	0	0	
V6	0	+1	
V7	+1	-1	
V8	+1	0	
V9	+1	+1	
Translation of coded level in actual limit			
Independent variables	Real Value		
	Low (-1)	Medium (0)	High (+1)
Amount of Kyron T-314 (%) X1	4	8	12
Amount of HPMC E-15 (mg) X2	90	100	110

All 9 batches were evaluated for the % drug release at 15 min. Hardness (kg/cm²) (Y1) and Disintegration time (Sec) (Y2) to find out effect of the both parameters (X1, X2)

•Independent variables

- X1-Amount of Kyron T-314 Ratio (mg)
- X2-Amount of HPMC E-15 (mg)

• Dependent variables

- Y1- Hardness (kg/cm²)
- Y2- Disintegration time (sec)

Composition of formulation (F1-F9) optimized batches

Ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Co-crystalline API (mg)	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
Kyron T-314 (%)	4	4	4	8	8	8	12	12	12
HPMC E-15 (%)	90	100	110	90	100	110	90	100	110
Aspartame (mg)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Mg. Stearate(mg)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Talc (mg)	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
Flavour (ml)	q.s								
Total (mg)	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

Evaluation of vonoprazan fumarate orally disintegrating tablets

1) Weight Variation

Twenty tablets were weighed individually and the average weight was determined. The % deviation was calculated and checked for weight variation as per IP. [9]

2) Thickness

Thickness of tablets is important for uniformity of tablet size. Thickness was measured using Vernier Calipers on 3 randomly selected samples. [9]

3) Hardness

The resistance of tablet for shipping or breakage, under conditions of storage, transportation and handling, before usage, depends on its hardness. The

hardness of tablet of each formulation was measured by Monsanto hardness tester. [10]

4) Friability

Friability is the measure of tablet strength. Roche friabilator was used for testing the friability using the following procedure. Twenty tablets were weighed accurately and placed in the tumbling apparatus that revolves at 25 rpm dropping the tablets through a distance of six inches with each revolution. After 4 min., the tablets were weighed and the percentage loss in tablet weight was determined.

5) Uniformity Of Content

Content of active ingredient in tablets was taken at random, was determined tablets were weighed and average weight is calculated. All tablets were crushed and powder equivalent to 8 mg was dissolved in 250 ml 0.1 N HCl and shaken for 20 min. solution was filtered and after suitable dilution using 0.1 N HCL,

absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 254 nm against reagent blank. Amount of drug present in one tablet was calculated. [11]

6) Dissolution Studies

The release rate of Vonoprazan Fumarate from floating tablets was determined using USP Dissolution Testing Apparatus II (Paddle type). The dissolution test was performed using 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl, at 37 ± 0.5 °C and 50 rpm. Aliquot volume was withdrawn from the dissolution apparatus hourly for 24 hrs. and the samples were replaced with fresh dissolution medium. After filtration and suitable dilution the amount of drug release was determined from the calibration curve.[12]

7) Stability Study

Stability testing of drug products begins as a part of drug discovery and ends with the demise of the compound or commercial product. To assess the drug and formulation stability, stability studies were done according to ICH guidelines. The stability studies were carried out on the most satisfactory formulations as per ICH guidelines. The most satisfactory formulation sealed in aluminum packaging and kept in humidity chamber maintained at 40 ± 2 °C / 75 ± 5 % RH for 1 month. At the end of studies, samples were analyzed for the drug content, in vitro dissolution, floating behavior and other physicochemical parameters.[12]

8) Solubility Study

The solubility was determined by weighing out 300mg of the compound (API) to this is added 2ml of the solvent interest, (such as water, phosphate buffer 7.2). Successive amounts of the solvents were added until the compound was observed to dissolve.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Solubility study

•The solubility of pure drug is checked in water and phosphate buffer 7.2 . Result is shown below.

•The solubility of co-crystals were checked in water. Mentioned co-crystals were prepared with different polymers and the result found that the solubility is improved. The result is shown below.

Sr. no.	Co-crystal	Solubility in water
1	Resorcinol	30 mg/ml
2	Catechol	35 mg/ml
3	Hydroquinone	50 mg/ml
4	Pyrogallol	35 mg/ml
5	Kyron T-314	65 mg/ml

•The solubility of co-crystals were checked in phosphate buffer 7.2. Mentioned co-crystals were prepared with different polymers and the result found that the solubility is improved. The result is shown below.

Sr. no.	Co-crystal	Solubility in phosphate buffer 7.2
1	Resorcinol	95-100 mg/ml
2	Catechol	85 mg/ml
3	Hydroquinone	100 mg/ml
4	Pyrogallol	55 mg/ml
5	Kyron T-314	80 mg/ml

FTIR Study

The FT-IR spectra of Vonoprazan Fumarate were analyzed. Drug and the final optimized formulation

were subjected to FT-IR spectroscopic analysis for compatibility studies and to ascertain whether there is any interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The IR spectra of drug were found to be identical. The FT-IR spectra of the pure drug

indicated that the characteristics peaks of drug were not altered without any change in their position, thereby indicating no chemical interactions between the drug and polymers used. The FT-IR spectra of final formulation is done. The obtained spectra are

FTIR spectra of drug and optimized formulation

Functional groups of drug and formulation

Functional Groups	Standard Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Vonoprazan Fumarate (cm ⁻¹)	Final Formulation Peak (cm ⁻¹)
C=N stretch	1600 – 1660	1635.64	1633.41
C-N stretch	1100 – 1350	1332.81	1328.71
C-H stretch	2850 – 3300	2754.35	2868.59
O-H stretch	2500 – 3300	3008.95	3082.65

Standard calibration curve of vonoprazan fumarate

Sr. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 272 nm (mean \pm SD)
1	0	0
2	4	0.166 \pm 0.003
3	8	0.318 \pm 0.004
4	12	0.485 \pm 0.002
5	16	0.638 \pm 0.004
6	20	0.799 \pm 0.006

Calibration curve of vonoprazan fumarate

Evaluation of factorial batches F1-F9

Batch	Weight variation (mg)(n=3)	Thickness (mm)(n=3)	Hardness (kg/cm^2)(n=3)	Friability (%) (n=3)
F1	149.6 \pm 1.85	3.18 \pm 0.04	4.5 \pm 0.14	0.54 \pm 0.03
F2	150.3 \pm 1.72	3.21 \pm 0.05	4.5 \pm 0.18	0.58 \pm 0.04
F3	149.8 \pm 1.64	3.16 \pm 0.03	3.9 \pm 0.12	0.51 \pm 0.03
F4	150.7 \pm 1.91	3.22 \pm 0.04	4.1 \pm 0.16	0.62 \pm 0.05
F5	150.1 \pm 1.58	3.19 \pm 0.03	4.2 \pm 0.13	0.56 \pm 0.04
F6	149.9 \pm 1.73	3.2 \pm 0.04	4.6 \pm 0.15	0.59 \pm 0.03
F7	150.5 \pm 1.66	3.24 \pm 0.05	3.8 \pm 0.17	0.47 \pm 0.02
F8	149.7 \pm 1.8	3.17 \pm 0.04	4.2 \pm 0.14	0.6 \pm 0.04
F9	150.2 \pm 1.69	3.23 \pm 0.05	4.7 \pm 0.16	0.53 \pm 0.03

Batch	Disintegration Time (Sec)	Wetting Time (Sec)	Drug content %
F1	30 ± 1.6	34.6 ± 1.8	98.2 ± 0.96
F2	40 ± 1.4	33.1 ± 1.6	98.1 ± 1.02
F3	40 ± 1.3	31.8 ± 1.5	97.6 ± 0.88
F4	49 ± 1.2	30.7 ± 1.4	97.2 ± 0.91
F5	50 ± 1.1	29.5 ± 1.3	96.3 ± 0.85
F6	55 ± 1.2	28.9 ± 1.2	97.5 ± 0.93
F7	38 ± 1.0	27.4 ± 1.1	98.4 ± 0.87
F8	35 ± 1.1	28 ± 1.2	97.3 ± 0.9
F9	32 ± 0.9	26.6 ± 1	98.3 ± 0.84

Drug release of factorial batches of F1-F9

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
30 sec	32.4 ± 1.6	34.8 ± 1.7	36.5 ± 1.5	39.2 ± 1.4	41.7 ± 1.3	44.3 ± 1.3	47.6 ± 1.2	46.1 ± 1.3	49.3 ± 1.1
2	58.7 ± 2.1	61.2 ± 2.0	63.9 ± 1.9	66.8 ± 1.8	69.4 ± 1.7	72.1 ± 1.6	75.8 ± 1.5	74.2 ± 1.6	77.6 ± 1.4
4	74.5 ± 2.3	78.1 ± 2.2	80.6 ± 2.1	83.4 ± 2.0	85.6 ± 1.9	87.9 ± 1.8	90.4 ± 1.7	89.2 ± 1.8	91.7 ± 1.6
6	88.6 ± 2.5	91.4 ± 2.4	93.7 ± 2.3	95.2 ± 2.1	96.8 ± 2.0	97.9 ± 1.9	98.8 ± 1.8	98.1 ± 1.9	99.3 ± 1.7
8	90.4 ± 2.2	93.2 ± 2.1	95.4 ± 2.0	96.7 ± 1.9	97.9 ± 1.8	98.8 ± 1.7	99.5 ± 1.6	99.1 ± 1.7	99.5 ± 1.5
10	92.1 ± 2.0	94.8 ± 1.9	96.7 ± 1.8	97.8 ± 1.7	98.6 ± 1.6	99.2 ± 1.5	99.8 ± 1.4	99.4 ± 1.5	99.7 ± 1.6
15	94.8 ± 1.8	97.3 ± 1.7	98.6 ± 1.6	99.3 ± 1.5	99.6 ± 1.4	99.8 ± 1.3	-	99.7 ± 1.6	99.8 ± 1.3
20	95.9 ± 1.7	98.1 ± 1.6	99.2 ± 1.5	99.7 ± 1.4	-	-	-	-	-
25	96.7 ± 1.6	98.9 ± 1.5	99.6 ± 1.4	-	-	-	-	-	-

Profile of cumulative frequency of F1-F9

CONCLUSION

The study successfully formulated Orodispersible Tablets (ODTs) of Vonoprazan Fumarate using the direct compression method. Superdisintegrants like Kyrion T-314, crospovidone, sodium starch glycolate, and croscarmellose sodium were effectively incorporated. FTIR analysis confirmed no drug–excipient interaction, indicating good compatibility. All trial batches showed satisfactory pre- and post-compression parameters. Among initial batches, F12 exhibited rapid disintegration and maximum drug release.

Further optimization using a 3^2 factorial design highlighted the significant role of Kyrion T-314 and HPMC E-15. Optimized batch F7 demonstrated the best performance with very fast disintegration and high drug release within 10 minutes. It also met all quality control parameters like hardness, friability, and weight variation. The formulation ensures rapid onset of action. Overall, Kyrion T-314 proved to be an effective superdisintegrant for ODT development.

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